

Post-synthetic modification of a metal-organic framework for dual naked-eye fluorogenic detection in aqueous medium

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Abstract

As a new generation of crystalline porous materials, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have received tremendous attention in recent years not only owing to their intriguing structures but also for their potential applications in gas storage, heterogeneous catalysis, drug delivery and fluorescent sensors.

The metal-organic framework (MOF) called UiO-66-NH₂ (**1**; UiO = University of Oslo) was post-synthetically modified by condensation with 1-pyrenecarboxaldehyde. The pyrene-tagged MOF (**1'**) exhibited ~3-fold enhancement in fluorescence intensity over the un-functionalized one with a new emission peak at 470 nm due to the formation of pyrene excimer within the framework. **1'** showed fast response time, excellent selectivity and sensitivity for sensing of biologically active anions like F⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻ in pure aqueous medium via fluorescence 'turn-on' mechanism. **1'** also displayed rapid, selective and sensitive detection of 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (TNP) in aqueous medium via fluorescence 'turn-off' mechanism. The excellent detection performance of **1'** in aqueous medium makes it a promising dual sensor material for real-field applications.

Keywords: Metal-organic framework, Post-synthetic modification, Anion sensing, Nitroaromatics sensing.

References

[1] R. Dalapati and S. Biswas, *Sens. Actuators, B*, 2017, **239**,759–767.